
THE IMPORTANCE AND CONNECTION OF PSYCHOLOGY AND LINGUISTICS IN THE PSYCHOLINGUISTICS

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Khazratkulova Ezoza Ismat kizi

Master's degree student of English department,

Chirchik state pedagogical university, Tourism faculty

E-mail: (khazratkulova@gmail.com) +998 90 4501137

Abstract.

Psycholinguistics presents many theories that explain how a person acquires language, develops and understands spoken and written speech not only in his own language, but also in a second language. The department of psycholinguistics is considered one of the youngest departments of linguistics and has been widely studied by a number of scientists and researchers in our country, and the role of psycholinguistic aspects in the methodology of teaching English is incomparable.

Key words.

psycholinguistics, psycholinguistic aspects, degree of connection between psychology and linguistics, psychological orientation, "people's spirit"

In order to determine the degree of connection between psychology and linguistics, it is necessary to think about the psychological direction in the theory of linguistics, which is the root of psycholinguistics. The above-mentioned German linguist W. von Humboldt believed that the main basis of psycholinguistics is the comparative-historical linguistics, which appeared in the middle of the last century, in contrast to the explanation of the essence of language on a logical basis. B. G. Steinthal, a student of W. von Humboldt, was recognized as the founder of the philosophy of language. As a result of the work of two famous linguists, the psychological direction tried to break away from the traditional logical direction in its early period. These grounds were defined as "the mutual compatibility of logical and grammatical categories is very weak." Taking this into account, it was considered that logic has a universal character and therefore cannot reveal the features specific to the language of a particular nation. According to linguists, logic is a hypothesis-based science, and linguistics is genetic in nature. It follows that if linguistics studies the "speech process", logic is not interested in this process. Proponents of the psychological direction recognized psychology as the

methodological basis of linguistics and neglected logic in most cases. B. G. Steintal, with the help of his teacher W. von Humboldt, saw the place of expression of the "people's spirit" and people's psychology in the language of mankind. For this reason, special attention was paid to the social nature. Since the psychology of this period was individual psychology, together with G. Shteintal and M. Losarus, he published the journal "Ethnic psychology and linguistics" to create and promote social psychology (ethnopsychology). At the beginning of the twentieth century, V. Wundt also tried to create the science of folk psychology as a methodological basis of linguistics, but the goal of forming it as a separate science was not realized. Despite this, the movement to rely on psychology in linguistics led to the opening of a number of directions. In particular, due to the desire to reveal the spirit of the people in linguistics, attention has been paid to the in-depth study of folklore, mythology, riddles, proverbs, sayings and folk customs expressed in them. Also, in the process of introducing the concepts and practices of associative psychology into linguistics, supporters of the psychological direction in many cases focused on live speech, the direct speech process, the inner side of the language, and the meaning of words and sentences. According to them, the study of live speech provides a convenient opportunity to understand the essence and origin of the language. Another linguist, V. von Humboldt, showing the difference between language and speech, said that in the process of studying living speech, although the representatives of a certain language speak a common language, at the same time, each of them has their own language. comes to a conclusion. Some supporters of psychology paid great attention to the concept of the spirit of language, that is, the inner form of language. It should also be noted that G. Shteintal tried to apply it to the history of language, and in his opinion, languages had a very rich internal form in prehistoric times. Later, this concept occupied a central place in the works of A. A. Potebnya, a major representative of the psychological trend in Russian linguistics.

However, behind the term "inner form" used in the works of A. A. Potebnya, not the concept of "people's soul" given by V. von Humboldt, but the "center of the image" which is the basis of the origin of the word is understood. For example, the inner form, the center of the image, which served for the emergence of the word "bravo", was a sign of "a job well done". Even now, the word "bravo" creates an image of an excellent student in the educational system. When explaining the emergence of language units, representatives of the psychological direction often use psychological terms such as "assimilation", "association", "apperception". For

example, the concept of "association", as A. A. Potebnya explained, is widely used in describing the origin of the word, etymology of the word. They were among the first researchers to focus on W. von Humboldt's opinion that speech should be made an object of linguistic investigation. For the theory of universal grammar founded by A. Marty at the beginning of the 20th century, he showed that all languages express the same psychological content and have the same internal structure, because any person, regardless of which language he belongs to, noted in his works that it has a general psychophysiological structure. The concept of the main task of linguistics, as proved by the views of A. Marty, should consist of a precise description and analysis of the content and mental functions expressed through the means of universal language.

At this point, while thinking about another approach - linguistic approach, it is considered as an approach that takes into account the limitations of information processing. In the linguistic approach, linguists work on the role and importance of linguistic structures in language processing. In this case, it is said about the dual and equally important rigor of linguistic analysis and psychological experimentation.

This research paper also examines the modularity or interactivity of this language processing system, and recent research examines the degree of modularity or interaction in the system. As linguists have generally favored the modularity hypothesis, psychologists have been increasingly attracted to interactive explanations of the principles of language and its learning.

Conclusion. Psycholinguistics, otherwise interpreted as the psychology of language, is the study of the relationship between linguistic factors and psychological aspects. Psychology is mainly concerned with the mechanisms of language processing, consciousness and reflection in the brain; that is, the factors that enable people psychologically and neurobiologically: to receive, use, understand and produce language. Psycholinguistics links the cognitive skills and processes necessary to create grammatical structures of language. So, psycholinguistics plays the role of heart in the activity with language. But in most cases, psycholinguistics is neglected in general or applied linguistics, communication studies or second language teaching.

LIST OF LITERATURE:

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